

ПРОФЕСІЙНА ОСВІТА

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**Adaptation of Reference Literature for Teaching Reading in English
to Students of Non-linguistic Specialties at an Advanced stage**

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Abstract.** The issue of adapting modern strategies and methods of teaching reading to the challenges of today is extremely important and voluminous. **The

purpose of our research is to systematize the theoretical prerequisites for the development of an algorithm for adapting texts for educational purposes. We believe that the use of educational texts for teaching reading should be based on a system of principles that will allow developing a clear algorithm for their adaptation to turn the text into educational material with a system of exercises. **The task** of the research is to adapt reference texts of a multidisciplinary character for the needs of teaching reading to students at an advanced stage of teaching English for professional purposes. **The object.** In the focus of investigation is teaching silent reading of educational kind, which represents careful insight into the meaning with the help of text analysis and is usually practiced on small texts, and the main task is the qualitative side of reading, completeness and accuracy of understanding. **Results.** We select and adapt reference texts on the peculiarities of European cuisine, in particular British cuisine, national dishes, and recipes for reading at an advanced stage. The texts have an interdisciplinary character, combining the content of linguistics, restaurant business, and the food technology industry. **Conclusions.** The algorithm for adapting reference texts of an interdisciplinary nature for teaching reading at an advanced stage of English for professional purposes is based on the following items: 1) classification of communicative competences; 2) on the determination of the type of reading; 3) on the use of reading strategies depending on the purpose of reading and the features of the text material; 4) on determining the levels of understanding of foreign texts; 5) on determining the strategy of formation of reading skills according to the levels of understanding of the text; 6) on general methodological requirements for educational texts. **The perspectives of the study** are aimed at elaboration of algorithm for adaptation of various kinds of text aimed for the students of different specialties and at different stages of foreign language proficiency.

Keywords: *algorithm for adapting reference texts, teaching silent reading, texts of a multidisciplinary character.*

Адаптація довідкової літератури для навчання читання англійською мовою студентів нелінгвістичних спеціальностей на просунутому етапі

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Анотація.** Постановка проблеми.* Питання адаптації сучасних стратегій та методів навчання читання до викликів сьогодення є надзвичайно важливим та об'ємним. ***Метою нашого дослідження є систематизація теоретичних передумов для розробки алгоритму адаптації текстів для освітніх цілей. Ми вважаємо, що використання навчальних текстів для навчання читання має базуватися на системі принципів, яка дозволить розробити чіткий алгоритм їх адаптації для перетворення тексту на навчальний матеріал із системою вправ. ***Завданням*** дослідження є адаптація

довідкових текстів мультидисциплінарного характеру для потреб навчання читання студентів на просунутому етапі викладання англійської мови для професійних цілей. **Об'єкт.** У центрі уваги дослідження знаходиться навчання читання мовчки, що становить ретельне проникнення в сенс за допомогою аналізу тексту та зазвичай практикується на невеликих текстах, а головним завданням є якісна сторона читання, повнота та точність розуміння. **Результати.** Адаптуємо для читання на просунутому етапі довідкові тексти про особливості європейської кухні, зокрема британської, національні страви та рецепти. Тексти мають міждисциплінарний характер, поєднуючи зміст лінгвістики, ресторанного бізнесу та харчової технологічної промисловості. **Висновки.** Алгоритм адаптації довідкових текстів міждисциплінарного характеру для навчання читання на просунутому етапі вивчення англійської мови для професійних цілей базується на таких положеннях: 1) класифікація комунікативних компетенцій; 2) визначення типу читання; 3) використання стратегій читання залежно від мети читання та особливостей текстового матеріалу; 4) визначення рівнів розуміння іноземних текстів; 5) визначення стратегії формування навичок читання відповідно до рівнів розуміння тексту; б) загальні методичні вимоги до навчальних текстів. **Перспективи** дослідження спрямовані на розробку алгоритму адаптації різних видів текстів, орієнтованих на студентів різних спеціальностей та на різних етапах вивчення іноземної мови.

Ключові слова: алгоритм адаптації довідкових текстів, навчання читання, тексти міждисциплінарного характеру.

Problem statement. In the modern method of teaching a foreign language, reading is considered as a powerful means of communication and knowledge, as an activity, as a result of which a person enriches his inner peace, receiving satisfaction and high motivation from reading. The improvement of reading skills occurs due to

the inclusion of special skills related to both the perception of the graphic side of texts and their understanding, that is, the integration of sense from the meanings of language signs. Thus, reading is a complex speech skill that consists in solving semantic problems. Mastery of different types of reading is an important component of reading culture. The teacher's goal is to develop the ability to extract information from texts of various types depending on the communicative task.

The formation of reading skills in English is not only a goal, but also a means of teaching. Teaching reading requires careful selection of appropriate strategies depending on the types of reading practiced for different purposes, on factors influencing the effectiveness of reading skills development, on the appropriateness of different tasks at certain stages of reading. The issue of adapting modern strategies and methods of teaching reading to the challenges of today is extremely important and voluminous [3].

Unresolved issues. In modern foreign language teaching methodology, a position has been developed, that in order to introduce students to reading in a foreign language, it is necessary to stimulate reading motivation and ensure its success using appropriate tasks for exercises. The quality of texts and the appropriate system of exercises play an exceptional role in developing reading motivation. We believe that the use of educational texts for teaching reading should be based on a system of principles that will allow developing a clear algorithm for their adaptation to turn the text into educational material with a system of exercises.

Formulating the goals of the article (task statement). The purpose of our research is to systematize the theoretical prerequisites for the development of an algorithm for adapting texts for educational purposes. The task of the research is as follows: to adapt reference texts of a multidisciplinary character for teaching reading to students at an advanced stage of teaching English for professional purposes.

Analysis of the latest research and publications. Throughout the history of the theory of foreign language teaching, the problem of effectively solving the issues of

selection and pedagogically appropriate use of texts for reading has always been relevant. This problem has not lost its relevance today (Bezkorovaina O., Basaj O., Bohachyk M., Boretska H., Dyshchakovska O., Fomenko T.M., Jumrukuz A., Makarska Ye., Lukjanchenko O., Nikolayeva S., Red'ko V.G., Shcherban I., Stukalo O., Trubicina O., Yeremenko T., Zapotichna R., Romanyuk O., et al.) [1-15]. Scholars consider the role and place of texts in the content of textbooks, investigate the issues of their effectiveness, substantiate quantitative and qualitative characteristics, etc.

The issue of foreign language teaching to the students of non-linguistic specialties lies within the integrating the latest educational technologies, such as the employment of the educational projects and game-based teaching methods, allowing to combine educational and cognitive activities with a real professional environment [1], like a project team work, the success of which relies on the coordinated efforts of all its members and their ability to share responsibilities effectively [13], the use of the latest multimedia technologies in teaching speaking, reading, listening and writing [15].

The use of interactive teaching formats, such as small group work, discussions, and training sessions combined with project-based teaching, student portfolio creation, and role-playing or business games, as well as the integration of multimedia presentations and Internet-based resources, enhances the effectiveness of FLT [12].

Modern requirements for foreign language training of future specialists in various fields cannot be met without the introduction of innovative approaches to teaching a foreign language, aimed at the development and self-improvement of the individual, the disclosure of his reserve capabilities and creative potential, which contribute to the activation of students' cognitive activity, improving their professional qualities, such as the ability to analyse, work in a team, defend their own views, etc. [5].

Further research is needed into ways of using various information and communication technologies and mobile applications to ensure the formation of reading skills in the process of teaching English remotely [3]. Therefore, it is still of great necessity to look for more innovative approaches to FLT, esp. new resources and various teaching situations [8].

Presentation of the primary research material. To implement the formation of communicative competence, it is necessary to form reading competence, that is, the ability to read authentic texts of different genres and types with different levels of understanding of the content in conditions of mediated communication [14]. For a holistic understanding of the importance of reading skills in the context of the formation of communicative competence, its structural components should be considered. Communicative competence includes: 1) speech competence, which involves mastering the following types of speech activity: listening, speaking, reading and writing; 2) language competence, which includes language knowledge (lexical, grammatical, phonetic and orthographic) and relevant skills; 3) discursive competence, which includes the ability to manage speech and structure it using thematic and logical organization, coherence, style, rhetorical effectiveness, etc.; 4) sociocultural competence, which includes knowledge of the sociocultural features of English-speaking countries, the formation of skills to distinguish the general and specific in the culture of the native country and the country whose language is being studied; 5) sociolinguistic competence - the ability to understand and produce verbal and non-verbal behavior that corresponds to a certain sociolinguistic context of a communicative situation [2].

Based on various criteria, the methodology distinguishes the following classifications of reading types: 1) by form: reading aloud (a means of developing reading techniques at the initial stage of teaching English, and a means of controlling intonation expressiveness, pronunciation, accuracy of understanding, identifying difficulties, and developing oral speech at subsequent stages of teaching) and silent

(the most important skill that everyone who learns a foreign language must acquire; it can be review, familiarization, study, search, informational, or training, depending on the goal and objectives of teaching); 2) by target orientation: educational and familiarization – search; 3) by method of revealing content: analytical (detailed study of the text with analysis of the language form) and synthetic (holistic perception of the content of what is read); 4) with the participation of the native language: translated and untranslated; 5) by the nature of the implementation of the content side of the perception and processing of the text: reading with incomplete and complete understanding; 6) by the nature of the organization of the activity: training and control; 7) depending on the volume: extensive (reading for pleasure, expanding knowledge or replenishing vocabulary) and intensive (for detailed understanding of what has been read); 8) by the fact of the relationship to the educational process: educational and real; 9) by the method of using a bilingual dictionary: reading with a dictionary and reading without a dictionary; 10) by the place of organization of reading: classroom and home [14].

Depending on the purpose of reading and the features of the text material, the following reading strategies are distinguished in methods of teaching foreign languages: 1) predicting: probable prediction of the content of the text based on the title, cover, illustrations or background knowledge in the context of working on the text; 2) monitoring: determining whether the reader understands the content of what has been read, otherwise rereading for the purpose of full understanding; 3) confirming: finding evidence of the accuracy of the previous prediction; 4) connecting: referring to previous reading, information or experience; 5) questioning: asking questions about the content of the text, which may include making predictions or predictions about each part of the text during reading; 6) skimming: reading to understand the general content or main ideas of what has been read; 7) scanning: reading to identify specific, detailed information (e.g., dates, names, etc.); 8) distinguishing: distinguishing important and unimportant secondary information; 9)

using context clues: reviewing the structure and content of the text (illustrations, punctuation, etc.) for the purpose of deeper understanding; 10) paraphrasing or summarizing: used during and after reading the text; 11) visualization: creating graphic images according to what has been read for a better understanding of the content of the text [7].

There are several levels of understanding of foreign language texts: 1) the level of fragmentary understanding (understanding the content of individual sentences at the level of individual paragraphs); 2) the level of general understanding (complete deep understanding of the content of what has been read); 3) the level of complete (detailed) understanding (own critical assessment and understanding of the emotional coloring of the content of what has been read); 4) the level of critical understanding (analysis and generalization of the ideological and thematic content and its connection with the general direction of the work) [14].

According to different levels of understanding of texts, the following strategies for developing reading skills are distinguished: 1) at the word level: highlight a number of derived words and their constituent elements, underline words or parts of words that are with words in the native or other foreign languages (for example, international words, borrowings, etc.), find words with certain affixes and reveal their meaning them and form derivatives from a common root, etc.); 2) at the sentence level: taking into account visual clues (for example, capitalizing words; numerals; negation; quotation marks; punctuation marks); grammatical markers (verb endings; finding words in the text that connect parts of a complex sentence (conjunctions, pronouns); taking into account word order in different types of sentences, etc.); 3) at the text level: supplementing the text with pictures, photos, diagrams, graphs, etc.; dividing the text into parts; searching for key information in the text; searching for words in the text that connect sentences with each other; 4) at the level of understanding cultural phenomena: developing skills in understanding realities,

knowledge of the country; comparative analysis of texts in English and the native language [3].

The main principles of selecting texts for textbooks for elective foreign language courses are the following: communicative value of the content of the texts; pragmatics and social effectiveness; scientific content of the texts; authenticity, which determines the selection of texts with normative speech patterns adopted in the country whose language is being studied; taking into account students' foreign language learning experience; accessibility and optimal amount of information in the texts; cultural relevance and cultural value of the content of the texts; educational, educational and developmental values of the texts [11].

Text adaptation involves its simplification, adaptation, facilitation or complication in accordance with the level of language and speech competence of students. When assessing the complexity of the text, not only its content aspect, but also the language aspect should be taken into account, respectively, strong text adaptation is distinguished (general qualitative change in the speech structure of the text), medium adaptation (making significant changes due to minor reductions and synonymous replacements of complex parts), weak adaptation (reduction of individual blocks of text while preserving its content core or with the delineation of certain content lines), conditional adaptation (removing complex parts to the petit with the preservation of the content sequence of the main part of the text) [11].

For the development of reading motivation, the quality of texts, their practical, general educational and educational significance play an exceptional role. The requirements for educational texts for reading are as follows: 1) the educational value of texts, their moral potential: texts should contribute to the education of students and the formation of moral and ethical norms; 2) the cognitive value of texts and the scientific nature of their content: texts should include factual material about the country and people whose language is being studied, as well as information from a wide variety of fields of human knowledge (popular science texts); 3) the

correspondence of the content of texts to the age and interests of students: the content of texts should be significant in the eyes of students of a particular age group, should correspond to the level of their intellectual development, cognitive and emotional interests; 4) an adequate ratio of new and known: the presence of known information in texts for reading greatly facilitates its perception and understanding by students, therefore, the texts should specify and expand the information already known to students; 5) the degree of accessibility of texts: an interesting text containing insurmountable difficulties loses any attractiveness in the eyes of students [4].

So, in the FLT methodology, it is recognized that the selection of educational texts must adhere to the main requirement – to be interesting and accessible, to stimulate the motivation of reading. The motivation and desire to read large texts are directly dependent on the students' sense of their progress in understanding increasingly complex extended texts with a stimulating understanding of the context, redundancy of information and multifaceted disclosure of the meaning of words. To stimulate the successful reading of progressively more complex and increasing texts, an appropriate system should be practiced, the nature of which is determined by the type of reading, the stage of teaching a foreign language, and the degree of language difficulty of the text.

Let's choose, for example, teaching silent reading of educational kind, which represents careful insight into the meaning with the help of text analysis and is usually practiced on small texts, and the main task is the qualitative side of reading, completeness and accuracy of understanding. Since the type of reading is entered with the help of the corresponding tasks, therefore, the wording of the tasks to the text is decisive. We select and adapt reference texts on the peculiarities of European cuisine, in particular British cuisine (Appendix A), national dishes (Appendix B), and recipes for their preparation (Appendix C) for reading at an advanced stage [6]. The texts have an interdisciplinary character, combining the content of linguistics, restaurant business, and the food technology industry.

I. Tasks related to the control of text comprehension. In tasks for texts for self-reading, the main thing is to solve semantic problems, and the most important tool for self-control here is the keys to the tasks. For example: "Read the text, find a sentence in it, which, in your opinion, contains the main idea. Check yourself on the key."

To control understanding, gestures or concessions, symbols (tests) or productive forms in the native language are used, which are introduced by tasks such as: "Read the text and say in Ukrainian that you learned about the features of English, Scottish and Irish cuisine."

"Activity" exercises, the tasks of which prompt specific actions: "Read the text and draw ... (choose a picture corresponding to the content). Read the recipe text and make this dish yourself. Read the text and show the corresponding dishes (ingredients of the dish) in the picture."

A system of tests, in particular multiple-choice tests and comparison tests, has a positive effect on reading motivation and speeds up the process of reading large texts. For example: "To each dish indicated on the left, add the number of the recipe made by you."

II. Tasks on citation from the text. When quoting, reading about yourself is combined with reading aloud or writing. For example: "Find in the text sentences corresponding to the following Ukrainian sentences." Citations can be used to confirm/refute facts of a factual nature and to solve problematic issues. For example: "Read the texts. In order to determine whether you understood the texts you read, find: a) in the first text, a sentence that summarizes the characteristics of the English kitchen; b) in the second text, a sentence from which it is clear why the British like to use in food ...; c) in the third text of the sentence, from which it is clear that ..."

At the senior stage, quoting indicates a deep understanding of the text, which implies a complete processing of information, for example: "Read the text and say what is special about the English kitchen. Justify your opinion with examples from the text." In some cases, through the citation of the text, there is a connection

between reading and oral speech: "Write sentences from the text, with the help of which you can give a detailed oral answer to the question given in the title."

III. Tasks related to the preparation of a plan for the text.

"Make a plan for this text. Arrange the points of the plan in accordance with the sequence of the narration. Determine how many semantic parts can be distinguished in the text. Make a plan in the form of theses, using the sentences of the text."

IV. Tasks related to question-and-answer exercises. Possible questions to the text, presupposing a quote in the answer, there are. finished material tasks: "Read the text and find the answers to the questions in it". Questions introducing the puzzle text: "Determine from which recipe this passage is taken. Find out why the dish is called that. Read and tell me what kind of dish this article is about."

A question revealing cause-and-effect relationships: "For what purpose? Why? On what basis?" A question asked before reading the text directs the reader's attention, a post-text question promotes the processing of specific information, helps reveal the main and essential details. Questions about the text predetermine the type of reading, in particular, questions about the actual side of the text and the subtext, as well as about details, presuppose studying reading. The ability to ask a meaningful question about the text is a proof of correct understanding. It is possible to offer students to read different texts and asks questions addressed to each other about what they read: "What did you read? What is it about? Did you like...? Why did you like/didn't you like it?"

V. Exercises aimed at developing anticipation based on the content of the paragraph, title, illustration, providing conditions for subsequent understanding (for example): "Look at the illustration and say what (what kind of kitchen, what dish) is going to be talked about in this text. Then read the text to the end and say to what extent your guess was confirmed".

Conclusions. The algorithm for adapting reference texts of an interdisciplinary nature for teaching reading at an advanced stage of English for professional purposes to the students of non-linguistic specialties is based on the following items:

1) classification of communicative competences (speech, language, discursive, sociocultural and sociolinguistic);

2) on the determination of the type of reading according to the classification according to the form, target orientation, the method of revealing the content, with or without the participation of the native language, the nature of the implementation of the content side of the perception and processing of the text, the nature of the organization of the activity, the fact of the relationship to the educational process, the method of using a bilingual dictionary, the place of the organization of reading;

3) on the use of reading strategies depending on the purpose of reading and the features of the text material: prediction, confirmation, combination, survey, quick review, detailed study, recognition, use of clues from the context, paraphrasing and generalization, visualization;

4) on determining the levels of understanding of foreign texts: the level of fragmentary understanding, the level of general understanding, the level of full understanding, the level of critical understanding;

5) on determining the strategy of formation of reading skills according to the levels of understanding of the text: at the level of the word, at the level of the sentence, at the level of the text, at the level of understanding of cultural phenomena;

6) on general methodological requirements for educational texts, in particular, the presence of educational value of texts and moral potential; cognitive value of texts and scientific content; appropriateness of the content of the texts to the age and interests of the students; an adequate ratio of new and known, as well as a measure of accessibility of texts.

The perspectives of the study go within the general problem of adaptation of educational text for the needs of stimulation of motivation in the process of foreign

language teaching, especially in teaching reading, precisely in elaboration various kinds of text aimed for the students of different specialties and at different stages of foreign language proficiency.

Appendix A

BRITISH CUISINE

British cuisine has preserved and brought to our days many traditional dishes. Their basis is meat, fish, vegetables, cereals. The British have a very diverse range of cold snacks, especially fish gastronomy, sandwiches. To this day, popular snacks – triangular sandwiches – have become one of the unshakable English traditions. Triangular sandwiches with cucumbers on white bread are considered classic. From the first courses, pureed soups and broths are widespread, they are an integral part of the daily meal. Spices and herbs in classical cuisine are used to a limited extent, although now English chefs are teaching the British to use a variety of dishes and spices.

The British eat a lot of meat: beef, veal, lamb, pork. It is baked whole with blood or cut into steaks and fried in a pan. Meat is always accompanied by gravy, Yorkshire pudding, baked and boiled vegetables (usually potatoes, carrots and cabbage) and pickles. Now this dish is served mainly on Sundays and is called Sunday Lunch.

English cuisine is characterized by an unusual way of cooking vegetables. A very common dish is cabbage with leeks, cooked only in salted water. To give such an unappetizing dish a more pronounced taste, the English invented ready-made sauces in the last century, which – from ketchup to Worcestershire sauce – can be found on every table. This is very convenient, because everyone can flavour the food as they wish.

There are many traditional dishes in English national cuisine. We cannot fail to mention sweet and savoury puddings, which are served with meat or for dessert, potato casseroles with beef, minced lamb, fish and roasts. Many traditional dishes are

served only on holidays. Among them, the popular Christmas pudding (made from lard, bread crumbs, flour, raisins, sugar, eggs and various spices; before serving, this pudding is poured with rum, set on fire and placed on the table while still burning), cross buns for Easter, potatoes with sausages for Guy Fawkes Day. Traditional holiday dishes also include stuffed turkey with a vegetable side dish, holiday cake, etc.

Some varieties of English cheese enrich the wide range of European cheeses with their original taste. The Anglo-Saxons are extremely fond of sweets. Such desserts as caramel pudding and creams are among the highest achievements of culinary art even by world standards.

Beer is especially popular among alcoholic beverages.

The “ritual” attitude to tea deserves special attention. This national drink was already popular in the 17th century, and it became widespread, probably because it helped to overcome the bad mood caused by the harsh climatic conditions, and also improved the taste of swamp water.

Scotland and Ireland also have their famous national dishes, in particular, oat pie. In Ireland, among the popular home dishes are potato pancakes boxty and a dish of Savoy cabbage colcannon. In these parts of the UK, patriotic feelings and romantic memories of the country of childhood play a big role in choosing a dish. Gourmets will appreciate the bouquet of flavour shades that molasses adds to dishes. Malt vinegar or dark brown cane sugar are all seasonings that we in Central Europe do not use.

Irish cuisine. Irish cuisine is characterized by simplicity. Northern Ireland, the “emerald island,” produces some of the best, most environmentally friendly products in the world. The proximity to the sea, the climate, and the countryside has a significant impact on the products common in Northern Ireland. Thanks to abundant rains, the pastures are always full of juicy grass, which is good for milk production, which in turn turns into wonderful cream, butter, and cheese. The green Irish hills

create an excellent basis for raising cattle, and the mild climate helps the cattle graze on the meadows all year round, and the meat turns out juicy and tasty. It is on the basis of such fresh lamb that traditional Irish stew is prepared.

The special soil and climate create ideal conditions for growing potatoes, which are one of the main products and symbols of Irish cuisine. Potatoes are an ingredient in many Irish soups, pies, kebabs, breads, rolls, pies and even pancakes. One of the most famous Irish dishes is colcannon (from the old name for cabbage) - made from mashed potatoes, chopped cabbage, onions and seasonings. Champy is a similar dish, but the potatoes are not chopped very finely and mixed with chopped herbs, onions, milk, butter, salt and pepper. Another traditional potato dish is boxty - potato pancakes made from grated potatoes, fried in a pan.

In the rivers and lakes of Northern Ireland there is an abundance of different fish: salmon, trout, perch, eel, pike. The sea is home to lobsters, shrimp, oysters and mussels, as well as all kinds of fish, including cod, rays, flounder, herring and mackerel. In addition to seafood, red seaweed (dulse) is harvested in the sea, which is traditionally used for food. The seaweed can be mixed with mashed potatoes (dulse champ).

In Spring, Irish or pearl moss (edible seaweed) is often harvested, which is used both fresh and dried.

Ireland has a lot of delicious traditional pastries. This is farce, which is baked from wheat flour with the addition of Hercules in the shape of a quarter of a circle (in translation this word means "one fourth"). Soda bread with its unusual sour taste (due to the use of buttermilk) is very popular. Potato bread is another traditional dish, served cold or fried in lard as a breakfast item. Barmbrack is a fruit bread, reminiscent of the Welsh bara brit, served with tea and butter.

Appendix B

SALADS AND APPETIZERS. *English salad* (made from boiled chicken meat, celery root, boiled mushrooms, mayonnaise, pickles, mustard, salt). *Aberdeen*

salad (made from canned salmon in soy sauce, canned cucumbers, boiled veal liver, smoked lamb, oatmeal). *Pickwick salad* (made from boiled chicken breast, mayonnaise, pickled mushrooms, pickles, chopped greens). *James Bond salad* (made from semi-dry martini, pickles, pineapple, chicken, celery, mushrooms, mayonnaise, mustard, parsley, salt). *Big Ben salad* (made from potatoes boiled in their uniforms), herring or anchovy fillets, onions, olive oil, vinegar, parsley, mustard, salt). *Rice and celery salad* (made from long-grain rice, low-fat cream, sour apples, celery stalks, lemon juice, salt, ground white pepper). *Maral* (made from boiled chicken, mayonnaise, celery, boiled mushrooms, radishes, pickled cucumbers, mustard, celery greens, lettuce leaves, salt). *Sandwich* (made from sandwich buns, sausage, hard cheese, small tomatoes, lettuce leaves, mayonnaise, parsley greens). *Scotch eggs* (made with ham, lard, breadcrumbs, toasted bread slices, eggs, anchovies, black pepper, salt). *Welsh cheese toast* (made with grated cheese, beer, butter, thick slices of bread, red pepper, mustard, egg yolks).

FIRST COURSES. *Vegetable soup* (made from beef leg meat (cut into thick slices), soup bones, green beans, fresh or frozen green peas, cauliflower, lean bacon, baby carrots, tomato, onion, celery root, leek stems, soup greens, parsley, salt, ground black pepper). *Lamb soup* (made from lamb, celery, carrots, turnips, onions, pearl barley, pepper, parsley, salt). *Lorraine soup* (made from broth, minced boiled chicken white meat, cream, blanched almonds, boiled egg yolks, grated fresh white bread crumb, lemon zest, nutmeg, salt). *Chicken and leek soup* (made from broth, chicken, leeks, rice, butter, parsley, salt, pepper). *Kalen skink soup* (made from milk, potatoes, Findon haddock, onions, butter, chopped parsley, salt, pepper). *Mussel soup* (made from fresh mussels, strong fish stock, dry cider, butter, flour, onion, parsley, black peppercorns, bay leaf, garlic, thyme, salt). *Tomato puree soup* (made from veal bones, tomatoes, milk, onion, celery, turnip, butter, leek, sugar, black peppercorns, lemon juice, herbs, salt). *Cheese soup* (made from white broth, grated cheddar cheese, onion, butter, flour, pepper, salt). *Oatmeal puree soup* (made from vegetable

broth, milk, oatmeal, bread, cream, butter, egg yolks). *Cabbage Broth* (made from meat broth, white cabbage, oatmeal, salt, pepper). *Burmese Ginger Soup* (made from strong chicken broth, ginger root, strong fish broth, celery leaves, partridge, green onions, black peppercorns, salt).

SECOND COURSES. *English Beef* (made from beef (thick or thin edge), turnips, white cabbage, onions, carrots, oil, salt, pepper). *Roast beef with Yorkshire pudding* (made from beef (thick edge), vegetable oil, salt; pudding (made from wheat flour, milk, eggs)). *English beefsteak* (made from beef (tenderloin), horseradish, fat, butter, vegetable oil, green onions, parsley, pepper, salt). *Shepherd's pie with rice and beef* (made from minced beef, boiled rice, broth, sour cream, grated hard cheese, tomato sauce, green peas, oil, carrots, onions, eggs, salt, pepper). *Lancashire dinner* (made from lamb neck, potatoes, lamb kidney, meat broth, onions, mushrooms, butter, salt, pepper). *Veal escalope* (from veal, eggs, ham, butter, crackers, salt). *Veal liver Birmingham style* (made from veal liver, bacon, butter, flour, fat, parsley, salt, pepper). *Roast pork with apple sauce* (made from boneless pork ham, sour apples, minced meat, breadcrumbs from wheat bread, onions, eggs, salt, sage). *Pork chops in fruit jelly* (made from pork, fruit juice (pineapple, orange, etc.), gherkins, lettuce, butter, pitted olives, gelatine). *Chicken baked in dough* (made from chicken, potatoes, broth, carrots, onions, celery root, butter, grated nutmeg, pepper, salt; dough: flour, butter, water, salt). *Chicken with eggs* (made from chicken for frying, spinach, large onion, chicken broth, eggs, butter, cream, vinegar, black peppercorns, cloves, allspice, salt; filling: breadcrumbs, chopped ham, melted butter, onion, dried basil, dried parsley, salt). *Chicken meat pies* (made from puff pastry, eggs; filling: boiled chicken meat, milk, onion, bacon, butter, flour). *English-style duck* (made from turkey, onion, liver, almonds, wheat bread, apples, milk, butter, eggs, smoked bacon, lemon, raisins, sage, paprika, cumin, ground black pepper, salt). *English-style roasted goose* (made from goose, lard, white bread (soaked in milk), onion, milk, oil, eggs, parsley, sage, basil, pepper, salt to taste). *English-style pike fillet* (made from

pike, boiled potatoes, caper sauce, butter, crackers, flour, ground black pepper, salt). *Stuffed herring* (made herring, fresh mushrooms, milk, crackers, butter, lemon, herbs, garlic, pepper, salt). *English cod* (made from fresh cod, potatoes, lemons, butter, vinegar, parsley, salt). *Scottish herring goulash* (made from fresh herring, onion, flour, lemon juice, ground red pepper, salt, parsley). *Fried crabs* (made from small boiled crabs, ghee, salt, ground nutmeg, allspice, mace). *Creamed spinach* (made from spinach, butter, fresh cream, salt). *Christmas pudding* (made with brandy, milk, raisins, caraway seeds, wheat bread crumbs, oranges, beef lard, peeled almonds, glazed cherries, premium flour, brown sugar, vegetable oil, candied lemon and orange peel, grated lemon zest and juice, eggs, ground cinnamon, ground cloves, allspice, salt; rum butter: butter, powdered sugar, rum, ground nutmeg).

BAKING AND DESSERTS. *Honey muffins* (made with wheat flour, honey, granulated sugar, margarine, crushed walnuts, ground almonds, eggs, baking soda; glaze: granulated sugar, crushed walnuts). *"Dundee" cupcake* (made from wheat flour, butter, powdered sugar, light-coloured raisins without pits, black raisins without pits, crushed large raisins with pits, candied cherries, assorted red, green, yellow candied fruits (i.e., orange, watermelon, melon peels), 50 g ground almonds, eggs, sherry or cognac, rum, coarsely ground almonds, baking powder, lemon zest, butter for greasing the mold and paper). *Apple cheese pie* (made from sour apples, flour, brown sugar, heavy cream, butter, cheddar cheese, water, butter, sugar, lemon juice and grated zest, ground cinnamon, salt, butter for greasing the mold). *Gooseberry puree with cream* (made from gooseberries, cream, water, sugar).

SALADS AND APPETIZERS. *Multi-coloured salad* (made from red lettuce, lemon, yellow lettuce, sherry vinegar, walnut oil, burdock oil, salt, ground black pepper). *Potato salad* (made from potatoes, mayonnaise, onions or apples, greens). *Pate "One to ten"* (made from potatoes, broth, fatty lamb, ground black pepper, salt; *dough*: flour, butter, eggs, water, salt).

FIRST COURSES. *Pea soup with beef* (made from meat broth, peas, beef, sour cream, oil, onions, parsley, pepper, salt). *Potato soup* (made from vegetable broth, potatoes, onions, butter, parsley, pepper, salt).

SECOND COURSES. *Irish meat* (made from potatoes, minced meat, bacon strips, vegetable oil, salt, ground black pepper). *Potato and meat stew* (made from lamb or beef, potatoes, onions, carrots, salt, ground black pepper, parsley, basil). *Potatoes with apples and pork chops* (made pork chops, onions, potatoes, butter, apples, eggs, salt, pepper, ground crackers). *Meat with porter and prunes* (made from beef pulp, beef broth, porter beer, pitted prunes, onions, carrots, rendered beef fat, parsley, wheat flour, a pinch, caraway sprigs, bay leaf, ground black pepper, salt). *Irish veal stew* (made from veal, potatoes, cabbage, onions, carrots, butter, leeks, celery, pepper, salt). *Irish stew (lamb with potatoes)* (made with lamb, potatoes, onions, parsley, bay leaves, ground black pepper, cumin, salt). *Limerick pork belly* (smoked beef, cider, mustard, gin, brown sugar, blueberries, salt). *Fried salmon* (made from salmon, cream, butter, dry cider, flour, parsley, salt, pepper). *Baked haddock* (made from poached fish, boiled rice, butter, eggs, pepper, salt). *Halibut fillet* (made from halibut, apple juice, cream, butter, fried mushrooms, celery, salt, paprika). *Colcannon with lard* (made from potatoes, lard, butter, sour cream, salt, nutmeg). *Colcannon with potatoes* (made from potatoes, cabbage, butter, fat, pepper, salt). *Potato pancakes* (from flour, potatoes, milk, frying oil, onion, eggs, pepper, salt). *Spinach with nettle* (made from fresh spinach, young nettle, cream, young carrots with herbs, onion, butter, roasted seeds or nuts, egg yolks, sugar, garlic, salt, pepper, nutmeg). *Irish pancakes* (made from milk, flour, granulated sugar, powdered sugar, frying fat, vegetable oil, cinnamon, rum, eggs, lemon, nutmeg).

PASTRY AND DESSERTS AND DRINKS.

Irish soda bread (made from kefir, wheat flour, rye flour, oatmeal, sugar, corn flour, baking soda, salt, ground coriander or rye flour, cream, baking soda, salt). *Orange whiskey dessert* (made from oranges, whiskey, condensed milk with sugar,

baked biscuits, dark chocolate). *Apple jelly* (made from apples, water, sugar). *Irish coffee* (made from water, coffee, whole cream, sugar, whiskey).

Appendix C

RECIPES

Colcannon with potatoes (ingredients: 500 g potatoes, 400 g cabbage, 70 g butter, 35 g fat, pepper, salt to taste). Boil the potatoes, but do not stew and let them stand. Put in the oven at 60-70°C. During this time, cut the cabbage into small pieces and stew in a small amount of fat. Mash the mashed potatoes until the mixture becomes homogeneous. Add the cabbage and mix. Serve with pieces of butter.

Pickwick salad (ingredients: 600 g boiled brisket, 250 g mayonnaise, 200 g pickled mushrooms, 4 pickled cucumbers, 8 g chopped greens). Boiled chicken breast fillet is cut into small pieces, cucumbers are diced, and mushrooms are cut into small strips, everything is thoroughly mixed, poured with mayonnaise. Garnish with greens.

Big Ben salad (ingredients: 500 g of potatoes, boiled “in their uniforms”, 125 g of herring fillets or anchovies, 1.5 onions, 50 g of olive oil, 10 g of vinegar, 6 g of parsley, 5 g of mustard, salt to taste). Peel the potatoes and cut into slices 1 cm thick. Cut the onion into slices as well. Cut the peeled herring fillet into large pieces. Mix all the ingredients and pour over the sauce of olive oil, vinegar and mustard. Mix again and sprinkle the salad with chopped parsley.

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